

STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT AND CHALLENGES IN IMPLEMENTING THE SCHOOL IMPROVEMENT PROGRAM IN JIGJIGA SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates stakeholder engagement and the challenges faced in implementing the School Improvement Program (SIP) in selected secondary schools in Jigjiga City, Ethiopia. Utilizing a mixed-method approach, data were collected through questionnaires, semi-structured interviews, focus group discussions, document analysis, and observations. The study population included 311 teachers, 4 principals, 4 vice principals, and various education office experts, with a sample comprising 160 teachers and key stakeholders. The analysis focused on identifying the roles of stakeholders in SIP implementation and the challenges faced by school leaders. Findings revealed that while school leaders exhibited low levels of engagement in strategic management and community involvement, challenges such as financial constraints, poor communication, and limited stakeholder participation significantly hindered effective implementation. The results highlighted the necessity for enhanced collaboration, better resource management, and increased commitment among stakeholders to overcome these challenges. Recommendations include fostering parent partnerships, improving communication strategies, and implementing a structured monitoring and evaluation program to support SIP initiatives. This study aims to inform educational stakeholders about the critical areas needing attention to facilitate the successful execution of SIP in secondary schools.

INTRODUCTION

Education has long served as a societal process, contributing to capacity development and the continuity of communities. It acts as a vital tool for acquiring skills, pertinent knowledge, and behavioral patterns essential for adapting to a dynamic world. Since the 1990 World Conference on Education for All, "Education for All" has remained a global concern (Grover, 2002). However, beyond providing access, enhancing the quality of education has become a central agenda at all levels of education, particularly at the primary level (Gamage, 2006).

Ensuring quality education has increasingly been prioritized in the strategic plans of developing nations. Although the definition and indicators of quality may vary among countries, quality is widely recognized as a pivotal factor in achieving the goals of education for all initiatives (World Bank, 2006). Jellema (2002) argues that a quality education system is one that accomplishes its goals, responds to the needs of children, communities, and society, and enhances students' ability to acquire knowledge and critical thinking skills. While definitions of quality vary according to different national contexts, UNICEF (2010) identifies five dimensions: the learner (including health and supportive parents), the learning environment (such as class size and physical conditions), content (student-centered and relevant curriculum), processes (teaching, assessment, and evaluation), and outcomes.

Similarly, in Ethiopia, concerns about the declining quality of education across all educational levels have been widely acknowledged by stakeholders, including the government (MOE, 2007). While commendable progress has been made in expanding access to secondary education, increasing from a 61.6% gross enrollment rate in 1999 to 91.3% in 2005/6 (MOE, 2005), schools have struggled to ensure educational quality. This is evident in the National Learning Assessments conducted in 2000, 2004, and 2008. For example, Grade 8 achievement scores declined from 41.1% in 2000 to 39.7% in 2004. The 2008 assessment further revealed that only 13.9% of students scored above the 51% passing standard, while a majority—62.1%—scored below this threshold (MoE, 2007).

To address this issue, the Ethiopian government launched a nationwide reform called the General Education Quality Improvement Program (GEQIP), aimed at enhancing the quality of education in primary and secondary schools (MoE, 2007). GEQIP comprised six major components: curriculum, textbooks, and assessment; the Teacher Development Program; the School Improvement Program; the Management and Administration Program; Information Communication Technology; and Civic and Ethical Education (Berry, 2009). A key strategy for promoting quality education is effective leadership at every level within the school system. The initiation of GEQIP indicates the government's focused effort on improving educational quality. Leadership is thus essential to bring transformative change through school improvement initiatives. According to Sergiovanni (1991), school principals play a central role in school improvement efforts.

Strong leadership is crucial in achieving a school's objectives. Glover emphasizes that school leadership significantly influences the institution's functioning. School leaders must take the initiative, as they serve as catalysts in ensuring the effective implementation of school improvement programs (Glover, 2000). The School Improvement Program (SIP), introduced in 1999 by the Ministry of Education, aims to enhance student outcomes in primary and secondary schools. Since its launch, schools have developed and implemented three-year strategic plans to improve student performance (MoE, 1999). The SIP is supported by documents such as the School Improvement Framework, the School Improvement Program Implementation Manual, and the School Improvement Guideline.

Since its implementation in 1999, SIP has provided valuable lessons across Ethiopian schools. Before initiating the second strategic planning cycle, the Ministry of Education reviewed the program to reinforce its effectiveness (MOE, 1999). This review contextualized and reaffirmed SIP's importance, with objectives including: (I) strengthening schools' capacity to identify priorities and develop improvement plans; (II) increasing school and community participation in resource allocation and mobilization; (III) improving the government's ability to deliver targeted school grants at the Woreda level; and (IV) enhancing learning environments by providing essential operational resources (MOE, 1999). School leaders play an indispensable role in the realization of the school improvement

program (Tigist, 2014). They are expected to guide schools effectively, ensuring that all activities and plans align with the institution's goals. Recognizing a gap in understanding leadership's role in SIP implementation, the researcher aims to assess the leadership role in SIP implementation in the selected Shek Abdisalam and Hussen Girre Secondary Schools.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

While studies on SIP practices, challenges, and leadership effectiveness have been conducted in Ethiopia, few have specifically focused on leadership roles. Frew Amsale (2010) explored SIP practices and challenges in Jimma's primary schools and identified school leaders as major challenges due to poorly designed SIP plans. Jemal Haji (2013) studied SIP in secondary schools of Asosa and highlighted performance and financial challenges. Seyoum Ararso (2014) assessed leadership effectiveness in SIP implementation in the Illubabor Zone and found school leaders had low effectiveness scores, below <1.49. Tigistu Awelu (2014) examined leadership perceptions of SIP effectiveness in Addis Ababa and concluded that school principals were less effective due to lack of experience and qualifications. While these studies assessed leadership performance and effectiveness, they did not address leadership roles specifically in SIP implementation. Thus, the researcher identified a gap and intends to evaluate leadership roles in SIP implementation at Shek Abdisalam and Hussen Girre Secondary Schools, where leaders are held accountable for either the success or failure of their institutions (Tigist, 2014).

1.3 Objective of the Study

The general objective was to assess the school leader's role in school improvement program in selected Junior and secondary schools in Jigjiga city administration. Specifically, the study was to:

1. To identify the stakeholders' role in SIP implementation.
2. To identify the challenges of school leaders in SIP implementation.

1.4 Research Questions

Accordingly, the study was designed to answer the following research questions:

1. To identify what role of stakeholders in School Improvement Program implementation in Shek Abdisalam and Hussen Girre Secondary Schools?
2. To identify what are the challenges in implementation of School improvement program in Shek Abdisalam and Hussen Girre Secondary Schools?

2. Literature Review

Principles of School Improvement Program

According to Geleta and Jote (2009), research in this area has identified numerous essential principles that contribute to school effectiveness and excellence. Based on recent efforts in school reform, several core principles have been outlined for school leaders aiming to enhance their institutions. These include having a clearly defined mission or set of goals; consistent monitoring of academic performance; support structures for all students, such as remedial programs for low achievers and enrichment initiatives for gifted learners; and a consensus among teachers and administrators regarding effective teaching and learning practices.

A unified educational philosophy and learning psychology should be prevalent, where cognitive development is balanced with students' social, emotional, and moral growth. Students are encouraged to take responsibility for their actions; teachers and administrators maintain high expectations and communicate them to both students and parents. Educators are encouraged to contribute significantly to school improvement, while administrators provide sufficient support, resources, and time for teacher development.

A spirit of teamwork should dominate, with strong interdisciplinary and interdepartmental communication. Teachers and administrators are acknowledged and rewarded for their contributions to school goals. The personal needs and interests of individual staff members are aligned with institutional expectations. Staff are given opportunities for creativity and professional challenge. There is a focus on continuous professional development jointly planned by teachers and administrators. The school maintains a safe and healthy learning environment with well-ordered classrooms. Parental and community support is evident, with active participation in school functions. The school serves as a learning hub for the broader community, reflecting its values and norms, and is seen as a community extension (Tamiru Jote, 2009).

School Improvement Committee

As Hopkins (in Harris et al., 2005) highlights, school improvement teams are integral to the sustainability of such efforts. Often termed “internal change agents” or cadre groups—borrowing from Schmuck and Runkel’s organizational development model in Oregon—these groups manage the daily operations of school improvement projects. They serve as a bridge between principals and actionable strategies. Typically, a cadre group comprises four to six staff members across different hierarchical levels. While the head teacher may be involved, the group should be broadly representative and distinct from existing administrative bodies to avoid groupthink. These members also participate in out-of-school training aimed at building teaching capacity.

Internal Conditions for School Improvement Program

Hopkins (2001) identified six key internal conditions essential for effective school improvement, emphasizing the need to strengthen these elements:

Staff Development: A comprehensive and coordinated strategy for professional development is vital, with classrooms as central venues for teacher growth. Staff development supports teachers in improvement efforts and directly enhances student learning.

Involvement: Research on effective schools shows that success correlates with a broad sense of involvement beyond just teachers. This includes students, parents, and the local community. For example, studies from Wales cited in Hopkins (2001) describe a “corporative approach,” incorporating both student participation and supportive parental involvement.

Leadership Practices: Leadership plays a critical role in school success (Hopkins, 2001). Recent perspectives extend leadership beyond the principal, advocating for distributed and transformational leadership models that emphasize empowerment over traditional hierarchies (Gronn, cited in Hopkins, 2001).

Coordination: A school’s ability to align teacher actions with shared goals is crucial. Effective communication systems and the creation of structured groups help sustain coordinated efforts across departments, ensuring strategic goal implementation (Hopkins, 2001).

Inquiry and Reflection: Schools that embed reflective practices into their improvement strategies can maintain focus on core priorities. These schools also better assess whether their policies deliver expected student outcomes, even amidst change.

Collaborative Planning: Successful planning is rooted in collaboration, not merely documentation. Through group planning, schools define goals, resolve differences, and create actionable strategies. The process itself often yields longer-lasting benefits than the actual plan (Hopkins, 2001).

Figure 1. Internal Conditions (Source: Seyoum Ararso, 2014).

External Conditions for School Improvement

Capacity Building: School capacity is defined as the collective competency of the institution to initiate meaningful change, which includes staff knowledge and skills, a collaborative professional culture, program alignment, and access to technical resources (Hopkin et al., 2001). Achieving whole-school capacity is challenging due to the uneven development of its structural, cultural, and human elements (Hadfield in Harris, 2005).

Policy Issue: As per Marzano (2003), policy serves as the guiding framework for action in the school improvement context. Hopkins (2001) argues that while policy cannot mandate what truly matters, local-level implementation is crucial to outcomes. Policies must be coherent, practical, and feasible across all levels. Moreover, policy effectiveness requires close monitoring. Hopkins et al. (1994) further assert that school improvement policies should remain focused on student achievement, consider contextual factors, build capacity, and encourage research-based implementation. Thus, schools must be offered diverse policy options aligned with broader system frameworks.

Challenges for School Improvement Program

Implementing school improvement is complex and may face numerous obstacles (Stoll and Fink, 1996). These include program complexity, staff turnover, leadership inefficacy, weak coordination, and limited long-term commitment. Other barriers include inadequate support

from higher authorities and minimal stakeholder engagement. According to Hussein and Postethwore (1994), these challenges vary by school characteristics and external contexts. In Ethiopia, although national efforts aim to improve educational access, the School Improvement Program (SIP) focuses on enhancing education quality through better student learning outcomes (MOE, 2007). Despite policy intentions, implementation proves difficult, creating challenges for SIP success.

1. **Lack of Commitment of School Leaders:** Many school principals lack proper educational leadership training. Even trained leaders often fail to effectively set a vision and coordinate staff toward goal achievement (MOE, 2007).
2. **Lack of Stakeholders' Participation:** Stakeholder involvement is critical in school planning, yet most plans are developed solely by principals. As a result, school missions and visions are not widely shared, hindering achievement of targeted student outcomes and ethical development (MOE, 2007).
3. **Lack of Conducive Environment in School:** Students need a secure and supportive environment to fully engage in learning. Schools must cater to both male and female students, fostering ethical growth and academic success by addressing their interests and ensuring safety (MOE, 2007).
4. **Lack of Educational Input:** The limited involvement of schools, stakeholders, and NGOs in providing educational materials has left many schools without necessary resources. This shortfall hinders teaching and learning quality (MOE, 2007).

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Description of the study area

Jigjiga, the capital of the Somali Regional State in Ethiopia, has 18 primary and 4 secondary schools. The selected schools for this study are Wilwal, Jigjiga High School, ShekAbdisalam, and HussenGirre.

3.2 Research Design

This study employs a mixed-method approach, emphasizing quantitative data, to assess leadership roles in implementing the School Improvement Program (SIP). A descriptive survey effectively captures current practices.

3.3 Sources of Data

Both primary and secondary data sources were utilized.

3.3.1 Primary Source: Participants included teachers, principals, vice principals, student councils, supervisors, SIP focal persons, and education office experts from the selected schools.

3.3.2 Secondary Source: Secondary data were obtained from documents, reports, educational statistics, and policy documents produced by educational authorities.

3.3.3 The Study Population: The population consisted of teachers (311), principals (4), vice principals (4), supervisors (8), student council members (24), and education office experts.

3.4 Sample and Sampling Techniques

3.4.1 Sampling Technique: Both random and purposive sampling techniques were used. Four schools were randomly selected, and samples included 160 teachers (51% of the population), all principals and vice principals, and selected student council members and supervisors.

3.4.2 Sample: The sample comprised 160 teachers, 4 principals, 4 vice principals, 6 supervisors, 1 education office expert, 4 SIP focal persons, and 4 student council members.

3.5. Instruments of Data Gathering

Data were collected using questionnaires, interviews, focus group discussions, document analysis, and observations.

3.5.1. Questionnaire: A structured questionnaire with closed and open-ended items was distributed to teachers, achieving a 100% return rate.

3.5.2. Interview: Semi-structured interviews were conducted with key stakeholders to gather in-depth qualitative data.

3.5.3. Focus Group Discussion: Focus group discussions with supervisors provided qualitative insights into SIP implementation.

3.5.4. Document Analysis: Relevant documents, including SIP manuals and strategic plans, were analyzed to supplement primary data.

3.5.5. Observation: Observations of school facilities and environments were conducted using checklists.

3.6. Methods of Data Analysis

Quantitative data were analyzed using frequency counts and percentages, with the aid of the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20, while qualitative data were thematically analyzed through narrative descriptions.

3.7. Ethical Consideration

The study ensured confidentiality and voluntary participation, with clear communication about the study's purpose to all participants.

3.8. Procedure of Data Collection

Data collection occurred in April 2015, following the selection of schools. Questionnaires were distributed, followed by interviews and focus group discussions. Observations were conducted to assess the physical environment of the schools.

4. Findings and Discussion

4.1. Backgrounds of Respondents

Overall, the chapter comprises of two major parts. The first part presents the characteristics of respondents in terms of sex, age, academic qualifications, position, name of the school and service year. The second part deals with the results of findings from the data which were gathered through the questionnaire, interview, document analysis, FGD and observation. This background examination of the study was important that leaders of schools should meet

criteria set by the ministry of education to perform their function properly. Thus, the school leader's background, skill and knowledge about the field of leadership can create the ability in developing different performances which lead to success and then achievement of SIP Implementation.

4.1.1. Socio- Demographic Description of the Teachers Respondents

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Description of the Teachers Respondents

Respondent Type	Description	Frequency	%
Teachers	Sex		
	1. Male	151	94.3
	2. Female	9	5.6
	Total	160	100
	Age		
	1. 20-30 years	86	53.75
	2. 31-40 years	62	38.75
	3. 41-50 years	10	6.25
	4. Above 50	2	1.25
	Total	160	100
	Qualification		
	1. Certificate	27	16.9
	2. Diploma	57	35.6
	3. Degree	74	46.2
	4. Master	2	1.25
Total	160	100	
Experience			
1. 1-4 years	39	24.3	
2. 5-8 years	104	65	
3. 9-12 years	9	5.6	
4. 13-16 years	7	4.3	
5. Above 16	1	0.65	
Total	160	100	

The characteristics of the teacher respondents in terms of sex revealed that 151 (94.3%) and nine (5.6%) teachers were males and females respectively and this indicates that there is low female participation. As Table 2, item 2 above showed, 86 (53.75%), 62 (38.75%), 10

(6.25%) and two (1.25%) of teacher`s age fall in the range of 31-40 years, 20-30 years, 41-50 years and 51 and above years respectively. In the above Table item 3 of the data tells about Certificate holders 27 (16.9%), Diploma holders 57 (35.6%), Degree holders 74 (46.2%) and Master holders of 2 (1.25).

As indicated in table 2, item 4, 39 (24.3%), 104 (65%), Nine (5.6%), Seven (4.3%) and One (0.65%) of teachers fell in the range of service year 1-4, 5-8, 9-12, 13-16 and above 16 years respectively. According to the career structure of teachers of our country, teachers are categorized into beginner teachers (1-4), Secondary teachers (5-8), higher level teachers (9-12), senior (leading) assistant (13-16) and senior (leading) teachers. Accordingly, as the data revealed the majority of teacher 104 (65%) were fall in the range 5-8 years of experience.

In the literature on leadership role in schools, there is strong evidence that success is associated with a sense of identification and involvement of socio demography status of the school. This socio demography is important for the competency of the school as an entity to bring about effective change based on the: knowledge, skills, qualification and disposition of individuals' staff; a professional learning community in which staff work collaboratively; program coherence; technical recourses. Thus, this is designed to strengthen the schools ability to manage changes, to enhance the work of teachers, and ultimately to improve students achievements.

4.1.2 Socio- Demographic Characteristics of interviewees and FGD Respondents

Table 2: Socio- Demographic Characteristics of interview and FGD Respondents

Description	Principals		Vice Prin		Superviso		SIP Focal		Stud Leaders		EO Expert	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Sex												
1. Male	3	75	2	50	6	100	4	100	4	100	1	100
2. Female	1	25	2	50	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	4	100	4	100	6	100	4	100	4	100	1	100
Age												
1. 20-30 years	3	75	4	100	4	66.6	3	75	4	100	1	100
2. 31-40 years	1	25	0	0	2	33.3	1	25	0	0	0	0
3. 41-50 years	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4. Above 50	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	4	100	4	100	6	100	4	100	4	100	1	100
Qualification												
1. Certificate	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2. Diploma	0	0	1	25	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3. Degree	4	100	3	75	6	100	4	100	0	0	1	100
4. Master	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	4	100	4	100	6	100	4	100	0	0	1	100

Experience													
1.	1-4 years	3	75	4	100	5	83.3	4	100	0	0	1	100
2.	5-8 years	1	25	0	0	1	16.6	0	0	0	0	0	0
3.	9-12 years	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4.	13-16 years	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5.	Above 16	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total		4	100	4	100	6	100	4	100	0	0	1	100

In the sample of the above table, there were 75% male and 25% female. 75% younger (20-30 years) and 25% middle ages (30-40 years). All of them had first degree holder and 75% had experience of 1-4 years and 25 % of 5-8 years. There were two male and female vice principals whose age was between 20 and 30 years of one degree holder and other of diploma holders with an experience of 1-4 years. As data indicated in the above table, all the supervisors and SIP focal persons were male and possessed first degree with an age below 40 years.

In the sample, there were four students who were male and below 20 years of age. Further, the study included one male, degree holder, EO expert of younger age with an experience below 1-4 years. This data is pertinent to the study because the standard of the education Bureau of the Somali regional state is that any supervisor and principal should meet the first degree holder minimum requirement. So that to have school improvement, the minimum requirements of the principals and supervisors should be degree holder (MoE). Furthermore, the ministry of education revealed that the school leaders should have minimum 8 years of experience with an age of 30 and above. This study indicated that the sampled schools met the requirements for leadership criteria of principals and vice principals but not the experience and age.

4.2 Role of Stakeholders in SIP Implementation

4.2.1. The Stakeholders Engagement and Management Domain

Table 3: The role of stakeholder’s engagement in management and leadership Domain

NO	Roles	Rating Scale							
		High		Medium		Low		TF	Total %
		F	%	F	%	F	%		
1	Managing schools through strategic vision	7	4.4	71	44.4	82	51.3	160	100
2	Managing resources of the school	20	12.6	78	48.4	62	38.8	160	100
3	Solving Problems behavior	7	4.4	15	9.4	138	86.3	160	100
4	On school management	3	1.9	51	31.9	106	66.2	160	100
5	On communicating in stakeholders and establishing management structures	4	2.5	141	88.1	15	9.4	160	100
6	To what role school leaders has collective responsibility and skill in shared leadership	22	13.7	64	40	74	46.3	160	100
7	The role to which school leaders make progress and solve in schools facing challenging circumstances effectively	36	22.6	61	38.1	63	39.4	160	100

As depicted in item 1 of the Table 3 above, the majority 82 (51.3%) of teacher respondents agreed that the role to which school leaders are capable of managing schools through strategic vision was at a low level and the rest 71 (44.4%) and seven (4.4%) of teacher respondents agreed that were at moderate and high level respectively. Supporting this idea, literature revealed that effective leaders provide motivation and encouragement that lead to success and they manage effectively in a changing educational environment to strategic vision (Sergiovanni cited in Temesgen, 2011).

With regard to item 2 of the same table above, the majority 78 (48.4%) of teacher respondents agreed that the role to which school leaders manage the school resources was at a moderate level and the rest 62 (38.8%) and 20 (12.5%) of teachers agreed that were at low and high level respectively.

But, the result from interview of EO expert interview revealed that as:

“These days, there is an improvement in using the budget in an appropriate and economical way.” 2016

Supporting this idea, the interview of one SIP Focal person of one sample school informed that:

“Not only principals who involve in managing and running the school budget, but also vice principals are responsible in controlling and monitoring budget of school especially school grant. But, at the same time secondary schools have scarce resource because, parents and community are not supporting the schools financially.”2016

Regarding this idea, Ignathios (cited in Masuku, 2011) stated that the leadership is nothing but it is successful accomplishment of intended organizational objectives by effectively and efficiently using the scarce resources. Masuku was also explained that the school is said to be SIP implemented if the role of leadership is the right things in a right way and strives to achieve its objectives using its resources optimally, economically, efficiently and sufficiently.

Item 3 of the same table above, 138 (86.3%) of teachers revealed that the role to which school leaders are active in leadership behavior to solve problems was at a low level and the rest 15 (9.4%) and 7 (4.4%) of teachers agreed that school leaders were able to confront challenges that they face in their day to day activities were at moderate and low level respectively.

In the FGD conclusion revealed that as their supervision and report from the education office 2014 and school reports of 2014 that the evaluation format of the leadership effectiveness in solving problems was medium level in the last year but the previous years was too low.

Item 4 of the same Table above, the majority 106 (66.2%) of teacher respondents agreed that the role of school leaders in managing the school was at low level and the rest 51 (31.9%) and three (1.9%) of teacher respondents agreed that were at moderate and high level respectively.

In an interview of one of the vice principals told that as:

“.....Principals and vice principals have great responsibility in managing their schools, and we do the same.....”2016

In an interview of the EO expert said that as:

“Initially schools were managed mechanically, but now with new knowledge and technology, concepts, efforts from education sector at all levels have improvement in leadership qualities...” 2016

Supporting this idea Katz (in Wossenu, 2006) stated that school leaders work to share leadership responsibilities and decision making throughout all levels of the educational organization.

As illustrated in item 5 of the same Table above, the majority 141 (88.1%) of teacher respondents agreed that the role to which school leaders are concerned in communicating in stakeholders and establishing management structures was at moderate level and the rest 15 (9.4) and four (2.5%) of teacher respondents revealed that as low and high level respectively. Regarding this idea, Harris (2005) stated that school leadership must build the capacity by developing the school as a learning community. Additionally, Sergiovanni (cited in Temesgen, 2011) stated that school leaders should develop the skill and talents of those around them.

As shown in item 6 of the same Table above, the majority 74 (46.3%) of teacher respondents agreed that the role of school leaders has collective responsibility and skill in shared leadership was at low level and the rest 64 (40%) and 22 (13.7%) of teachers agreed that as moderate and high level respectively. Regarding this idea, Katz (cited in Wossenu, 2006) stated that the role of leaders be successful only when they are equipped with certain managerial skills in getting things done through people.

As indicated in item 7 of the same table above, the majority 63 (39.4%) of teacher respondents responded that the role to which school leaders make progress and solve in schools facing challenging circumstances effectively was at a low level and the rest 61 (38.1%) and 36 (22.6%) of teachers agreed that school leaders solve conflict through peaceful discussion as moderate and high level respectively.

In an interview of one of the principals explained as:

“.....in the beginning there were certain conflicts means before SIP and many conflicts remained unsolved, later when SIP was implemented the relations among stakeholders have been increased and peaceful and harmonic environment is prevailed and certain conflicts are being solved peacefully.....”2016

In the FGD with the supervisors, emphasized the same and concluded that these days conflicts are being resolved peacefully due to coherent link is strengthening across the schools.....

4.2.2. Community Participation Domain

Table. 4: The role of stakeholders engagement in the Community Participation Domain

NO	Roles	Rating Scale							
		High		Medium		Low		Total F	Total %
		F	%	F	%	F	%	TF	TP
1	The role of school leaders in engaging community work	20	12.6	79	49.4	61	38.2	160	100
2	The role of school leaders encourages parents- partnership	14	8.8	15	9.4	131	81.9	160	100
3	The role of school leaders encourages promoting education	10	6.3	48	30	102	62.9	160	100
4	The role to which school leaders encouraging parents contribution to school	17	10.7	69	43.1	74	46.2	160	100
5	The role of school leader promoting activities to open their door to the community	42	26.3	61	38.1	57	35.7	160	100

Item 1 of the Table 4 above, the majority 79 (49.4%) of teacher respondents agreed that the role to which school leaders work in community engagement was at moderate level and the rest 61 (38.2%) and 20 (12.6%) of teacher respondents agreed that were at low and high level respectively. Regarding this idea, literature of school improvement committee (Harris et al; 2005) revealed that SIP Focal persons should be active in advising on the benefits of education and in encouraging parents to send their children to school so as to increase access and reduce dropout.

Item 2 of the same Table above, the majority of the teacher respondents 131 (81.9%) agreed the role in which school leaders encourage parents- partnership was at low level and the rest 15 (9.4%) and 14 (8.8%) of teacher respondents agreed that were at moderate and high level respectively. Regarding this idea, literature of SIP Domains revealed that those schools leaders that are able to create positive relationships and partnership with their wider parents can create a supportive climate for learning.

Item 3 of the same Table above, 102 (62.9%) of teacher respondents agreed that the role to which school leaders encourage promoting education was at a low level and the rest 10 (6.3%) and 48 (30%) of teacher respondents agreed that were at high and moderate level respectively.

Regarding the FGD supervisors result and conclusion, mentioned that:

“SIP Focal persons are often participating in school management, but the capacity and activities of SIP committee members to promote and create awareness in parents and community are nominal....”2016

Additionally, in an interview with one secondary school principals indicated that:

“Few of SIP Committee members come only after several invitations and take part in the meetings and involve in decision making on certain important issues of school. But, still in this aspect their contribution is not as expected.” 2016

Item 4 of the same Table above, the majority 74 (46.2%) of teacher respondents agreed that the role to which school leaders encourage parents contribution to school was at a low level and the rest 69 (43.1%) and 17 (10.7%) of teacher respondents agreed that at moderate and high level respectively.

In an interview of one of the SIP focal persons revealed that as:

“Parents support through providing resources at moderate level..... but many do not come and involve in school development or improvement.....”2016

In an interview of one of the student leaders informed that:

“.....resources, such as financial and material support from parents is very low particularly in secondary schools.”2016

Regarding this idea literature revealed that communities and PTAs need to play important roles in all aspects of education from raising resources to managing schools (MOE, 2005). MOE (2006) also revealed that school cannot succeed without the support of the parents and community.

As can be seen from item 5 of the same Table above, 61 (38.1%) of teacher respondents agreed that the role of school leader in promoting activities to open their doors to the community was at moderate level and the rest 57 (35.7%) and 42 (26.3%) of teachers agreed that at low and high level respectively.

In document analysis, the three year strategic plan of the SIP revealed that; if the role of school leaders were not ready to welcome the community with full interest and respect on the community or stakeholders may not have interest to come to school and work with schools and this might in turn affect the collaboration and positive relationship between school leaders and school communities which is very important in facilitating the implementation of school improvement program.

4.3. Challenges Affecting School Leaders role in Implementing SIP

Table 5: The challenges of the leadership in SIP Implementation

NO	Roles	Rating Scale						Total F	Total %
		High		Medium		Low			
		F	%	F	%	F	%	TF	TP
1	Financial Challenges	8	5	71	44.4	81	50.6	160	100
2	Challenges of Communication	21	13.2	78	48.8	61	38.1	160	100
3	Challenges of level of commitment of the school	4	2.5	51	31.9	105	65.6	160	100

	leaders									
4	Challenges of participation of stake holders and community	5	3.1	141	88.1	14	8.8	160	100	
5	Challenges of creating conducive school environment.	37	23.2	61	38.1	62	38.7	160	100	

Item 1 of Table 5 above, the majority 81 (50.6%) of teacher respondents agreed that the school financial constraints were the challenge for the leaders in implementing SIP.

Item 2 of the same Table above, 78 (48.8%) of teachers agreed that the school poor communication were a challenge for the leaders to implement SIP. and the rest 61 (38.1%) and 21 (13.2 %) of teachers revealed that sampled school leaders communication at low and high level respectively. Concerning this idea, literature revealed that, meaningful engagement and dialogue with staff in their day-to-day working lives facilitates effective communication (Duignan, 2006).

As depicted in item 3 of the same Table above, 105 (65.6) of teacher respondents revealed that a challenge of commitment to implement the SIP and the rest 51 (31.9%) and 4 (2.5%) were at moderate and high level respectively. Supporting this idea, Day et al., (2010) explained commitment as it is one of the most key attributes of school leader`s role in the SIP implementation.

As can be seen from item 4 of the same Table above, 141 (88.1) of teachers respondent agreed a challenges in participation of stake holders and community in articulation of school to implement SIP and the rest 14 (8.8%) and 5 (3.1%) were at low and high level respectively. Supporting this idea, Duignan (2006) suggested that, the articulation of vision necessarily involves role of leaders sharing their hopes, desires and expectations with the members of the school community, and establishing the participation of an organizational culture that supports the participation of all stakeholders. Ubben and Hughes (1997) also explained that the success of any organization depends on having a clear vision which is accepted by the participation of staff and other stakeholders.

Item 5 of the same table above, 62 (38.7%) of teacher respondents agreed that the there was a challenges of the creating conducive school environment. In literature review, the MOE prepared a document revealing that schools should be prepared based on the needs and interest of students secured their school environment (MOE, 2007).

An interview of one principal states that:

Really SIP implementation has the challenge of the stake holder's participation. Education offices and regional educational bureaus are not actively engaging the implementation process, 2016

In FGD discussion of supervisors, it was found that the major problems of the SIP implementation are the financial, commitment of school leaders, SIPC are not active and less role of the education office in this issue.....

In literature review, the major challenges of the SIP implementation are; lack of commitment, stake holder participation, conducive environment and educational input.

In document analysis of the school annual reports indicated the major challenges of the SIP implementation were a problem of financial, commitment, stake holders participation, weak linkage of SIPC and school leaders and lack of awareness.

In open ended questions, 90 % it was indicated that the major problems of the SIP implementation is the financial and commitment challenges. Thus, in this open ended they draw possible solutions of empowering the commitment of the school leaders, enough financial resources and participation of the concerned stake holders.

School improvement program is very complex that it might be hindered by various impediments that challenge the implementation. In research literature, these are lack of commitment, lack of stake holder's participation, lack of conducive environment and lack of educational inputs. From the result that, inadequate financial resource, insufficient communication which lacks transparency among leaders and the staff, low level of commitment of school leaders, inability of school leaders to fully involve the school community in the articulation of school vision were the major challenges that affect the school leader's role in implementing SIP. Additionally, as it could be concluded from the interview result, the absence of clear understanding of the procedures of SIP plan preparation, lack of guidelines and frameworks in some schools and lack of parents and community supports were also some challenges in sampled schools.

It is obvious that all this challenges can negatively affect the implementation of SIP and in turn the teaching learning process and students' achievement. Therefore, the junior and secondary school leaders should strive to eradicate or minimize these challenges by evaluating themselves through feedbacks given to them in the day to day activities.

5. Summary of Findings

This study assessed the roles of leadership and stakeholders and the challenges they face in implementing the School Improvement Program (SIP) in four selected schools in Jigjiga City administration. The research involved 160 teachers, school leaders, education officers, and student representatives using questionnaires, interviews, FGDs, and document review.

It was found that the role of school leaders in leadership and management of SIP was low level. This was as managing schools to strategic vision (51.3%), solving problems behavior (86.3%), school management (66.2%), collective responsibility and skill in shared leadership (46.3%) and making progress and solve in schools facing challenging circumstances effectively (39.4%). In addition to this, two roles were found as moderate level that is managing school resources (48.4%) and in communicating in stake holders and establishing management structures (88.1%).

It was found that the role of school leaders in community participation of SIP was low level. This was the roles of encouraging parent-partnership (81.9%), encouraging promoting education (62.9%), and encouraging parent's contribution to school (46.2%). In addition to this, two roles were found as moderate level that is engaging community work (49.4%) and 38.1% in opening door to community (38.1%)

The major challenges of the school leaders in SIP implementation were financial problem (50.6%), challenge of communication (48.8%), low commitment (65.6%), moderate participation of stake holders (88.1%) and challenge of creating conducive environment (38.1%).

6. Conclusions

Although a safe and healthy school environment was well-supported, leadership was weak in strategic management and community involvement. These gaps, along with limited stakeholder engagement and persistent financial and communication challenges, hinder the successful implementation of SIP. The lack of collaboration and poor resource utilization risks compromising educational quality and SIP objectives.

7. Recommendations

- The practices of school improvement program is not free from various challenges and in needs continuous assessment of existing conditions of the practices to suggest the possible solutions for the problems encountered its implementation. Therefore, it is better to recommend that school leaders, educational experts, JCEO and other stakeholders to draw the possible solutions of the challenges.
- Parents should feel their contribution of knowledge; contribute to a building fund through parent's partnership.
- It is recommended good communication and commitment for school principals and supervisors for successful implementation of the SIP
- It is recommended that education office should design the monitoring, evaluation and supervision program of the SIP implementation in a planned and practical way.
- It is recommended that students, teachers, education office and the Jigjiga municipality participate cleaning of the school.
- Finally, the researcher recommends a more detailed and comprehensive study in the area to strengthen the result of the findings

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